

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

**MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY**
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

PP-037

**Therapeutic potential of medicinal plants for Alzheimer disease treatment:
Special emphasis on acetylcholinesterase inhibition.**

Sneha R Patil¹, Jyoti P Jadhav^{1,2*}

¹Department of Biotechnology, Shivaji University, Vidyanagar, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India-416004.

²Department of Biochemistry, Shivaji University, Vidyanagar, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India- 416004.

*Corresponding Address: jjpbiochem@gmail.com

Abstract: Alzheimer's (AD) is one of the most common age-related neurodegenerative diseases in the world. Presently about 33.9 billion people suffered and it is concluded that it may get triple in upcoming years. Characteristic features of AD include accumulation of beta-amyloid plaque and hampered activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE). Several plants are reported for their neuroprotective, memory enhancing and anti-depressant properties. These are impressive source of bioactive molecules recognized for their pharmacological properties. Of late, medicinal plants are being accepted widely because of fewer side effects and significant properties compared to synthetic drugs. In present studies different 35 plant species were screened for the inhibition of AChE enzyme which is collected from various localities. Amongst these *Carissa carandas* exhibited maximum inhibition 87.59 ± 1.34 %. Subsequently *Royal ponica*, *Manjifera indica*, *Couroupita guianensis*, and *Rosa indica* shown remarkable AChE inhibitory activity ranges between 75 % to 56%. These prominent five species were further studied for their anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory activity using in-vitro models. This investigation resulted that highest inhibition potential plant species have significant anti-oxidant capacity. It also has utmost anti-inflammatory properties. *Carissa carandas* was selected as potential source of AChE inhibitors with their notable antioxidant capacity. It has remarkable neuroprotective property which can be utilized for symptomatic treatment of AD. Since these plant extracts are able to act on multiple therapeutic targets of AD, further evaluation is required to identify the bioactive ingredients, assess their safety and bioavailability in in vivo animal models.

Keywords: Neurodegenerative disease, Alzheimer's disease, acetylcholinesterase inhibition, medicinal plant, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

